

NOTES

Oxovanadium and Oxouranium Complexes of 3-7 Dimethyl 7-Hydroxy Octane-1-al

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Manuscript received 20 February 1979, revised 11 February 1980,
accepted 19 May 1980

3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al forms 1 : 2 complexes with $\text{VO}_2(\text{II})$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ and their structures have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, conductometric, *pH* metric, spectrophotometric and infrared studies. Stability constants of these complexes as calculated by Bjerrum method were found to be 1.08×10^{-2} and 1.00×10^{-2} for $\text{VO}_2(\text{II})$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ complexes respectively.

Metal complexes of 3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al were studied for the first time by the authors. 3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al is an aldehydic monoterpene alcohol¹. Having an aldehydic group and a hydroxyl group, it shows great tendency towards complex formation. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of metal complexes of vanadyl and uranyl ions with 3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al and their stabilities were calculated by Job's and Bjerrum methods.

Experimental

3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al, which was procured from M/S. H. Kelkar Co., Kerala was purified by column chromatography and its purity was further checked on T.L.C. plates.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR (B.D.H) grade. A 0.1M standard stock solution of vanadyl sulphate was prepared in doubly distilled water and a 0.1M stock solution of uranyl nitrate was prepared in ethanol. Standard stock 0.01M solution for 3-7 dimethyl 7-hydroxy octane 1-al (ligand for our purpose) was prepared in ethanol.

All conductometric studies were carried out on Toshniwal conductivity bridge model CLOI/02A with a dip type cell. An Elico *pH* meter model LI-10 was used for *pH* metric titrations. Hydrogen and glass electrodes were used for *pH* metric determination. Spectrophotometric studies were carried out on Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 type of spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr disc on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 in the region 4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} .

The complexes were isolated in aqueous ethanolic and ethanolic media. Ethanolic solution of ligand and aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate were mixed in 2 : 1 ratio. Similarly ethanolic solution of ligand and uranyl nitrate were mixed in 2 : 1 stoichiometric ratio. The solutions were refluxed on water bath for 48 hours, on cooling greenish powdery mass was separated out for vanadyl complex and greenish yellow crystals of uranyl complex were separated out. The complexes were washed several times with the solvent and vacuum dried. The complexes were microanalysed for carbon and hydrogen and observed values were in good agreement with the calculated one. These values are given below :

	%of carbon		%of hydrogen		%of metal	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Vanadyl complex	23.3	23.2	3.9	3.6	11.05	11.36
Uranyl complex	32.4	32.1	5.6	5.3	35.31	35.35

Results and Discussion

Reverse conductometric titrations² at 0.01M to 0.1M concentrations for metal and ligand were performed at room temperature. *pH* metric titrations were performed by Bjerrum method as modified by Irving and Rossotti³. The complexes were stable at *pH* 6.5 to 8.2. Spectrophotometric studies were carried out by Job's method⁴ of continuous variation at 540 nm and 490 nm for green and yellowish green complexes of vanadyl and uranyl ions. The complexes obey Beer's law under the concentration range 0.005M to 0.01M.

The spectrophotometric studies of the complexes were performed at 540 nm and 490 nm for vanadyl and uranyl complexes respectively. Transitions are different for both the complexes which are helpful for identification and quantitative analysis of the metal ions. Wave number and frequency of the monochromatic light were found to be in the range of 20.408 cm^{-1} and 6.122 cm^{-1} . The molar extinction coefficients (Σ) of the complexes were found 300 lit/mole, cm and 350 lit/mole, cm for vanadyl and uranyl complexes respectively.

Information regarding the nature of bonding was obtained by subjecting the ligand and complexes for IR studies. According to the structure of hydroxy citronellal, two positions may be prone to coordinate with metal ions, they are aldehyde group and hydroxy group. In both of these complexes the bands at 3600 cm^{-1} (due to hydroxyl group) and at 1650 cm^{-1} (due to aldehyde group) disappears.

The hydroxycitronellal therefore must be acting as bidentate ligand.

The metal ligand stability constants were calculated by Job's method⁵ of formula

$$K = \frac{X}{(a_1 - X)(b_1 - X)} = \frac{X}{(a_2 - X)(b_2 - X)}$$

where a_1, a_2 are the concentrations of metal and b_1, b_2 are the concentrations of ligand at different dilutions.

Values of stability constants were further confirmed by Bjerrum method⁶ as modified by Irving and Rossotti

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v'' - v') N + E^\circ + TL^\circ (Y - \bar{n}A)}{(v'' + v') \bar{n}ATM^\circ}$$

All the above studies confirmed the complexation ratio to be 1 : 2.

Acknowledgement

The author's thanks are due to C.S.I.R. for the award of a S.R.F. to one of us (M.N.)

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Determination of Stability Constants of 5-Methyl-Salicylidene-*p*-Methylaniline Complexes with Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

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Manuscript received 21 April 1979, revised 17 April 1980, accepted 12 June 1980

IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline was prepared by the method described in literature², and was repeatedly crystallised. (Observed m.p. 106°, Reported m.p. 106°).

Dioxan used was purified by usual method reported in literature³. The medium of titration was 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

The metal perchlorates were prepared from the metal carbonates of A.R. grade supplied by S.D. Lab. Chem., Bombay, using perchloric acid of A.R. grade. All these were standardised complexometrically⁴ by E.D.T.A. titrations. All the measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The Corning Model 12 with a combined glass electrode and a calomel electrode was used.

The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in the earlier communication⁵. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and *pL*. The appropriate corrections for the H^+ ion concentrations have been made as per the work of Irving and Mahnot⁶ and the values have been accordingly modified. Appropriate ion corrections were made at high *pH*. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in *pH* meter readings even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A value was plotted to get the formation curve. The formation curve extends over a range of $0.35 < \bar{n}_A < 1.95$ and is wave-like. The value of pK_1^H , which corresponds to the association of phenolic (OH) group, was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$, while that of pK_2^H , which corresponds to the association of proton to imino-nitrogen was